

Milestone:

M3.1 Outcome of consultation on applied quality metrics published. A report will be put together on the state-of-play across Europe

Lead Participant:

CRG

Author:

Ivo Gut & Jeroen Belien

Due:

30 Nov 2020

Date Of Completion:

31-01-2021

Means of Verification

Whalley JP, Buchhalter I, Rheinbay E, Raine KM, Stobbe MD, Kleinheinz K, Werner J, Beltran S, Gut M, Hübschmann D, Hutter B, Livitz D, Perry MD, Rosenberg M, Saksena G, Trotta JR, Eils R, Gerhard DS, Campbell PJ, Schlesner M, Gut IG. Framework for quality assessment of whole genome cancer sequences. Nat Commun. 2020 Oct 7;11(1):5040. doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-18688-y. PMID: 33028839; PMCID: PMC7541455.

Link to work in progress on survey ([folder](#))

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes

We have published an article describing a set of five QC metrics that can be used to assess the quality of tumor/normal whole genome sequence analysis. A survey on QC metrics used across the 1+MG WG4 participants has been closed and requires further scrutiny.

Project participants & others

Ivo Gut, Jeroen Belien (also survey participants)

Next action steps

In depth analysis of the Survey of the QC Measures of 1+MG WG4 (Deliverable due end of May 2021).

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